

Paper 12**A STUDY ON DIGITAL MARKETING AND ITS CHALLENGES****Shwetha N S¹ & Vinutha H K²**¹Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0003-3645-8999;

Email: shwethaprashanth93@gmail.com²Assistant Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4583-0572,

E-mail: vinutha.srinivasuniversity@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Since organizations have started utilizing cutting-edge technologies, digital marketing has grown in popularity. Digital marketing is a non-traditional virtual platform, primarily on the Internet, used to advertise goods and services, communicate with clients, and detect and comprehend user demands using digital technology and gadgets. It is a well-known and successful method of online business promotion for the growth of a company's brand. A product or service is primarily advertised to create awareness of its utility in the minds of potential buyers. In the past few years, the advertising business has seen a considerable transition as a result of globalization and the resulting changes in consumer purchasing patterns. While digital marketing is a tool for corporate expansion, there are some obstacles or hurdles that it must overcome. The study continues with challenges, such as problems of high competitors, poor internet connection, etc, emerged in the field of marketing from implementation of digital marketing.

Keywords: digital marketing, challenges, technologies and internet.

1. INTRODUCTION:

A wide range of business options are now possible through the Internet. Aside from sharing a personal birthday photo, one can easily reach existing clients and draw in new ones using social media. It's incredible how quickly and easily digital media can disseminate knowledge and support corporate growth [1]. Digital marketing development and technology advancement are intertwined. The first email of its kind, paved the way for people to transmit and receive information via a variety of devices [2]. In the 1980s, there was already enough computer storage to handle enormous volumes of client data. As opposed to relying just on limited list brokers, businesses were choosing to leverage database marketing techniques online. Because these databases make it possible for companies to track customer information more successfully, they have altered how buyers and suppliers interact. But the manual approach performed worse [3]. Without utilizing the Internet or social media platforms, businesses promoted their products or services through print media, radio and television advertisements, business cards, billboards, and a variety of other similar approaches [4]. Traditional marketing techniques have a hard time connecting with consumers and influencing their purchase behaviour. Digital marketing is utilized to achieve goals for promoting a firm on multiple online media [5]. Digital marketing refers to advertising campaigns that appear on a computer, phone,

tablet, or other electronic device. In addition to social media posts, paid social ads, display ads, online videos, and search engine marketing, it might also appear in other places. Billboards, magazine adverts, and direct mail are examples of "traditional marketing," which is frequently contrasted with "digital marketing." Unexpectedly, traditional marketing is frequently used to refer to television [6].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Gautam H (2014), With the growing number of internet users, combined with the mobile and digital revolutions, digital marketing has become an inseparable part of human life. When compared to traditional marketing methods, digital marketing provides advantages in terms of reach. Efficiency and cost effectiveness Companies are concentrating and expanding their use of to enjoy creativity, innovation, loyalty, and a large consumer base [5]. **Gangeshwer D. K (2013)**, e-Marketing is described by technological dependability, security and privacy concerns, maintenance costs as a result of a constantly evolving environment, greater pricing transparency and increased price competition, and global competition as a result of globalization [6]. **Anbumani, S., & Sankar, G. (2017)**, the study aims to provide a visual representation of how digital marketing strategies are developed and perceived by consumer segments. It aims to provide key indicators of successful digital marketing strategies. Advertisements in digital media were considered. Advertisements in the digital media have been considered for this purpose [7]. **Mishra, C. K. (2020)**, The study focused on digital marketing to meet people's current needs, which were limited to optimum and safe internet usage, which is now regarded as one of the basic rights of humankind [8].

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The study contrasts how quickly globalisation has changed the world with the global implications of digital marketing. Digital marketing platforms have a bright future and more knowledge than ever. Health safety has always come first when using technology to address important problems like the spread of infections. Digital marketing's outcomes have demonstrated that working online can occasionally be a more flexible and goal-driven option. It has been determined how much more can be sacrificed or what adjustments must be made in light of the problems in order to make the solution more foreseeable, manageable, and efficient [9].

4. OBJECTIVES:

Understand the various channels of digital marketing. Comparison of traditional marketing and digital marketing. Importance of digital marketing. Understand the various channels of digital marketing. Comparison of traditional marketing and digital marketing. Importance of digital marketing are to understand the various channels of digital marketing, to focus on the basic comparison between traditional and digital marketing, to discuss the effects of various forms of digital marketing on the firm's sales and other activities and to show the various advantages of digital marketing to the customers.

5. RESEARCH METHODOGY

The approach was based on secondary data and literature review. Secondary data sources were the reports of the various seminars, journals, workshop information, and other relative information published on other internet sites.

6. DIGITAL MARKETING:

The promotion of brands to engage with potential customers via the internet and other digital communication channels is known as digital marketing, sometimes known as online marketing. As a marketing channel, this encompasses text and multimedia messaging in addition to email, social media, and web-based advertising [10].

7. TYPES OF DIGITAL MARKETING

1. Search Engine Optimization (SEO): Probably the first thing that comes to mind when people consider various forms of digital marketing is search engine optimization (SEO). Online businesses are essentially at the whim of search engines like Google, Bing, Yahoo, and others. An effective SEO strategy can drive a lot of organic traffic to a website. In order for material to be among the top results on a search engine results page, it must be optimised for SEO (SERP) [11].

2. Search Engine Marketing (SEM): EO is not the only strategy for boosting search engine traffic. A product can be advertised in search engines and made to show up in paid search results thanks to search engine marketing (SEM). On SERPs, search engines typically place paid results above organic results. They resemble organic results almost exactly, with just a few minor visual variations. For example, Google displays a tiny "Ad" label next to the relevant URL [11, 12].

3. Social Media Marketing (SMM): Social media is without a doubt the king of digital content in the twenty-first century. As a result, if you want to advertise a B2C firm, it's one of the most crucial sorts of digital marketing you should concentrate on. People can use social media to stay in touch with friends and family, obtain the latest news, and follow topics that interest them in addition to using it as a medium for marketing. You can pick from a wide variety of social networking networks, including Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, and many others. To advertise your company there, you must locate those that are pertinent to the niche you are targeting [13].

4. Content Marketing: Another form of digital marketing you can employ to advertise a business online is content marketing. Since you produce information that the audience discovers by accident while surfing the web, content marketing is actually an indirect kind of advertising. Making viewers interact with the information by reading, sharing, and commenting on it is the core objective of content marketing. It can also be used in conjunction with other forms of digital marketing, including SEO or SEM. For the best outcome, you can, for example, structure the text around specific keywords [14].

5. Email Marketing: Since you communicate with customers through their personal email accounts, email marketing is a unique form of engagement. Even though email marketing is

one of the most established forms of digital advertising, it is still incredibly effective. It's a great approach to boost client retention and upsell to current clients [15].

6. Online Advertising: Since the beginning of the internet, digital marketers have used online advertising. The most popular method of online advertising is placing banners or adverts on websites in the same niche. To automatically deliver adverts on other content websites, you can use internet platforms like Google AdSense. The settings of the websites your adverts display on can typically be customised by ad networks depending on information such as keyword, geography, audience demographics, and other factors [15].

7. Affiliate Marketing: By outsourcing your marketing to outside service providers, affiliate marketing enables you to lessen your marketing workload. You only pay for conversions in affiliate marketing once your affiliate closed a deal and the customer made a purchase. Affiliate marketers handle all of the associated marketing tasks, including landing page creation and banner placement. The fact that there is no initial investment required and you may choose the conditions and commission rates for affiliates is probably affiliate marketing's strongest feature [16].

8. Viral Marketing: All of the forms of digital marketing listed in this article are used in viral marketing. The goal of viral marketing is to produce a post, video, meme, or other type of short-form material that spreads like a virus over the internet. You must promote the same information quickly across a variety of platforms, including Twitter, YouTube, blog posts, and newsletters, to create an effective viral marketing campaign [17].

8. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TRADITIONAL MARKETING AND DIGITAL MARKETING:

- **Low cost** - While advertisements in newspapers, television, and other media are expensive, online advertising is considerably less expensive than traditional marketing.
- **Real-time results** provide digital marketing an advantage over traditional marketing because the former may produce results quickly while the latter makes you wait a long time before producing any. You can easily track and view everything with online marketing, including the amount of visitors, conversion rate, busiest time of day, and bounce rate [18].
- **Brand development** – Digital marketing has an additional advantage when the issue of brand image between traditional marketing and digital marketing emerges. It loses to web marketing since there isn't as much space available and there aren't as many adverts as there are in conventional marketing.
- **Greater Exposure** - Any conventional marketing strategy, such as television advertising or newspaper ads, is only able to target a specific region's population or geographic area. As opposed to this, online advertising can reach a large audience, if not the entire world.
- **Quicker Publicity** – Digital marketing provides real-time results, allowing you to receive notoriety right away and, even if you don't, to identify which of your ads aren't performing well. With every passing nanosecond, digital marketing acts as a chain reaction, bringing you a new audience and a new customer.

- **Easy Analytics** – Digital marketing makes it incredibly simple and quick to measure marketing activities. Through Google Analytics, you can quickly determine which tactic is effective and which isn't..
- **Works for every stage or field** – Even start - up firms with a small workforce may handle their advertising and marketing efforts using digital marketing, which is impossible to do with traditional marketing [19].

9. FINDINGS:

- Small businesses are being left behind under the digital marketing concept.
- Lack of time and resources continues to block small business owners
- Gaining and keeping customers is the top marketing goal
- Due to online marketing, buyers are affected by defective products.

10. SUGGESTIONS:

- Improve technical advancement in promotion of digital marketing.
- Provide a transparent and good service to the consumer before and after purchase.
- Creating awareness among the people about digital marketing.
- Complete description needs to provide about the product to the online shoppers.

11. CONCLUSION:

The rise in internet usage, combined with the mobile and digital revolution, has made digital marketing an integral aspect of modern life. Digital marketing has advantages over traditional marketing strategies in terms of reach, affordability, and efficiency [20]. Digital platforms that are actively used include the internet, websites, mobile devices, television, SMS, and others. Companies are focused on and expanding the use of digital platforms to promote their goods and services in order to benefit from creativity, innovation, customer loyalty, and a sizable consumer base [21].

REFERENCES:

- [1] Diez-Martin, F., Blanco-Gonzalez, A., & Prado-Roman, C. (2019). Research challenges in digital marketing: sustainability. *Sustainability*, 11(10), 2839.
- [2] Chaffey, D., & Patron, M. (2012). From web analytics to digital marketing optimization: Increasing the commercial value of digital analytics. *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, 14(1), 30-45.
- [3] Sivasankaran, S. (2013). Digital marketing and its impact on buying behaviour of youth. *Hindu*.
- [4] Khan, R. Z., & Nawaz, H. (2021). Impact and Challenges of Digital Marketing during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Gorteria Journal*, 34(8), 31-39.
- [5] Gautam H (2014), “Ethical issues in digital Marketing”, *Global Journal for Business Analysis*, Vol. 3, No. 10, ISSN – 2277-8160.
- [6] Gangeshwer, D. K. (2013). E-commerce or Internet Marketing: A business Review from Indian context. *International Journal of u-and e-Service, Science and Technology*, 6(6), 187-194.

- [7] Anbumani, S., & Sankar, G. (2017). Digital marketing and its challenges. *Airo International Research Journal*, 12, 2.
- [8] Mishra, C. K. (2020). Digital marketing: Scope opportunities and challenges. *Promotion and Marketing Communications*, 1-24.
- [9] Kumar B.(2014), “Impact of Digital Marketing and E- Commerce on the real Estate Industry”, *International Journal of Research in Business Management*, Vol. 2,No. 7, pp – 17 – 22.
- [10] Khan M.S., and Mahapatra S.S., (2009), “Service quality evaluation in internet banking: an empirical study in India”, *International Journal of Indian Culture and Business Management*”, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 30 – 46
- [11] Chaffey, D., & Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2012). Digital marketing: strategy. *Implementation*.
- [12] Merisavo M. (2006), “The effect of digital marketing communication on customer loyalty: An integrative model of research propositions”, Helsinki School of Economics Working papers, Helsinki school publications.
- [13] Evans, D., Bratton, S., & McKee, J. (2021). *Social media marketing*. AG Printing & Publishing.
- [14] Geng, R., Wang, S., Chen, X., Song, D., & Yu, J. (2020). Content marketing in e-commerce platforms in the internet celebrity economy. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 120(3), 464-485.
- [15] Soegoto, E. S., & Fahreza, T. H. (2018, August). Email marketing as a business promotional media. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 407, No. 1, p. 012182). IOP Publishing.
- [16] Singhal, K., & Anand, A. (2021). Analysis of YouTube channel analytics and affiliate marketing with operating system. In *Advances in communication and computational technology* (pp. 1527-1537). Springer, Singapore.
- [17] Reichstein, T., & Bruschi, I. (2019). The decision-making process in viral marketing—A review and suggestions for further research. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(11), 1062-1081.
- [18] Bala, M., & Verma, D. (2018). A critical review of digital marketing. *M. Bala, D. Verma (2018). A Critical Review of Digital Marketing. International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*, 8(10), 321-339.
- [19] Rėklaitis, K., & Pilelienė, L. (2019). Principle differences between B2B and B2C marketing communication processes. *Organizacijų Vadyba: Sisteminiai Tyrimai*, (81), 73-86.
- [20] Pelegrin, M. A. L., & Mansueto, R. R. (2021). Digital Marketing Challenges and Opportunities: SMEs Insights. *International Journal on Social Innovation & Research*, 12(1), 1-1.
- [21] Herhausen, D., Miočević, D., Morgan, R. E., & Kleijnen, M. H. (2020). The digital marketing capabilities gap. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 90, 276-290.